

Contemporary art, painting and artists of the 20th century

Art has enjoyed a stage of constant evolution and change during the past century, where avant-garde pictorial movements have tried to reflect the social situation of each era through the brush and the particular vision of renowned artists.

Painter [Chaim Steg](#) shares that painting is the art of graphic representation par excellence of the history of mankind. Brushstrokes of emotion, protest, romanticism or nostalgia complete the collections of art galleries around the globe that saw, in the last century, a turbulent period of war, peace and, above all, change.

Chaim Steg claims that the 20th century was a transition of trends and sub-trends that are linked to the social events that mark each period. Thus, the avant-gardes were the starting point of a time of artistic experimentation in which Expressionism stands out. This trend had its birth with the Norwegian Edvard Munch and culminated in the works of renowned contemporary artists, such as the Austrian Gustav Klimt, Oskar Kokoschka, Egon Schiele and Otto Mueller.

Subsequently, Cubism emerged, a movement that in Spain had one of the greatest exponents of it, Pablo Picasso from Malaga, who narrates times of war and peace with his own brush with paintings that are already part of the history of art. This school, which had already begun to emerge through the hand of the Frenchman Paul Cézanne, was joined by names such as Georges Braque, Juan Gris, María Blanchard and Fernand Léger.

According to [talented painter](#) Chaim Steg, after the First World War (1914-1918) and the Second (1939-1945), contemporary art reached a modernist plenitude with the evolution of the avant-garde to abstract works, and that found in the United States some of its great representatives, such as Jackson Pollock. In this period, neo-figurative and neo-representational tendencies also developed, such as that of the Irishman Francis Bacon, who sought to capture the dark period of war and personal suffering through an uneven line and pictorial deformation.

The sixties, which marked the beginning of an era of color that lasted until the early years of the 1980s, had its artistic epicenter in New York with the appearance of the so-called pop-art movement, with Andy Warhol as its greatest exponent. A psychedelic period full of realism that was not obscured neither by the Cold War nor by the global conflicts that fill the pages of the history of those two unrepeatable decades.

Chaim Steg claims that in the era of technological proliferation and the triumph of digital over analog, contemporary art is in good health thanks to the talent of new creators, who continue to represent history through their particular view of the world. Now, these artists try to capture the user's attention with [their work](#) and cause a feeling of surprise and doubt at what they have in front of them.